

Understanding neurodivergence.

Recommendations for autism and ADHD in eating disorders: Guidance for clinical teams

About this guide:

Working with people experiencing eating disorders can be clinically complex. When neurodivergence is also part of the picture, formulation and treatment may require additional flexibility, curiosity and understanding.

Clinicians often describe uncertainty about how autism or ADHD may shape eating disorder presentations, engagement with treatment, or responses to standard interventions. We also know that, without this understanding, neurodivergent differences may sometimes be misinterpreted as resistance, non-compliance, lack of motivation, or unwillingness to receive treatment for eating disorders.

Our aim is to support clinicians and services in recognising neurodivergent differences and needs relating to autism and ADHD, and adapting care in ways that improve engagement, safety and treatment outcomes.

In this guide, you will find:

1. Recommendations for adapting clinical care

- Screening for autism and ADHD
- Adaptations to eating disorder treatment
- Working collaboratively with neurodevelopmental and ADHD services
- ADHD medication: benefits, risks and considerations

2. Further information for clinicians

- What is neurodivergence?
- The biology of neurodivergence
- Recognising autistic and ADHD traits
- How neurodivergence might impact eating disorder presentation
- How can autism influence eating disorders?
- Autism beyond restrictive eating disorders
- How can ADHD influence eating disorders?
- Recognising neurodivergent needs during eating disorder treatment
- Further training and resources
- Further reading

1. Recommendations for adapting clinical care

Eating disorder treatment may be more effective when adapted to meet neurodivergent needs. Adaptations do not mean reducing hopes for change or recovery. Instead, they aim to remove unnecessary barriers to engagement, understanding and participation.

The recommendations below highlight areas where adjustments may be helpful. They are not intended as a checklist that will apply to every person. Neurodivergent people vary in their needs, preferences and strengths, so adaptations should be discussed collaboratively and reviewed over time.

Screening for autism and ADHD

Some patients may already have a diagnosis of autism or ADHD. Others may show neurodivergent features but remain undiagnosed due to long waiting lists, limited access to specialist services, masking, or presentations that are not recognised as autism or ADHD.

Neurodivergent needs are important regardless of formal diagnosis. Where autism or ADHD traits appear to be affecting eating, treatment engagement, communication, sensory experience, emotional regulation, or daily routines, clinicians can consider making reasonable adaptations based on observed and reported needs.

If you or your patient are noticing possible neurodivergent traits, you could consider using a brief screening tool. Increasingly, some services are using screening tools as part of standard assessment procedures to help guide treatment planning at an earlier stage.

Two brief screening tools often used in clinical settings include:

- **AQ-10** — Autism Spectrum Quotient; screens for autistic traits
- **ASRS** — Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale; screens for ADHD traits

These tools are not diagnostic, but they may indicate whether referral for a full assessment could be helpful. Screening should be used alongside clinical judgement and discussion with the patient, rather than as a substitute for understanding their individual needs. Where waiting lists are long, clinicians may still consider reasonable adaptations based on observed and reported needs.

Adaptations to eating disorder treatment

The following areas may be useful to consider when planning care:

1. Sensory processing

Sensory sensitivities can influence appetite, food acceptance, mealtimes and tolerance of clinical environments.

Practical strategies may include:

- considering quieter, calmer environments during meals and therapy sessions
- reducing sensory overload where possible, including noise, lighting, temperature, smells or crowded spaces
- allow and normalise the use of sensory supports such as fidgets or weighted items
- exploring sensory preferences around food textures, flavours, smells, color and temperatures
- introducing new foods gradually alongside familiar or “safe” foods
- considering ways to support regulation if exercise needs to be limited, such as grounding activities, a rocking chair, music, art, sensory boxes or other agreed sensory strategies

2. Emotion regulation

Neurodivergent individuals may experience strong emotional responses, overwhelm or shutdown, particularly when environments or treatment tasks feel unclear, unpredictable or unmanageable.

Clinicians can support regulation by:

- validating, and exploring distress rather than immediately challenging it
- anticipating situations that may be dysregulating and reducing avoidable sources of distress where possible
- making difficult situations as predictable and clear as possible in advance
- pacing sessions and allowing breaks
- helping patients to explore, name and understand emotions, triggers and early signs of overwhelm
- teaching distress tolerance, grounding and soothing skills
- considering the potential role of impulsivity when risk planning

Some clinicians use the **ALVS** approach during distress:

Attend — give full attention

Label — name what you observe

Validate — acknowledge feelings

Soothe — support regulation

3. Executive functioning

Executive functioning differences can affect in the treatment context meal planning, appointment attendance and therapy related homework.

Practical strategies may include:

- establishing predictable routines for therapy sessions and meals
- providing reminders for appointments or tasks
- breaking goals down into smaller, more manageable steps

- offering written summaries or visual supports
- reducing decision-making load where possible
- allowing additional time where possible, including slowing the pace of treatment or individual sessions
- supporting patients who feel stuck due to choice, uncertainty, action paralysis, decision paralysis or not knowing where to start

4. Communication

Communication differences can lead to misunderstandings between clinicians and neurodivergent patients.

Helpful approaches include:

- using clear, literal language and avoiding idioms or figurative phrases
- offering written summaries or visual supports
- asking specific, concrete questions rather than broad open-ended ones
- interpreting eye contact, expression or tone with caution, as these may differ in neurodivergent patients
- considering a communication passport to record preferences; checking understanding collaboratively rather than assuming agreement

5. Co-occurring challenges

Autism and ADHD can be associated with co-occurring challenges. These may include anxiety, low mood, masking-related exhaustion, shame, low self-esteem, sleep difficulties, or sensitivity to perceived criticism or isolation.

Practical strategies may include:

- considering the impact of masking, compensation and exhaustion on treatment engagement

- screening for co-occurring conditions where clinically indicated
- using compassion-building strategies where shame or self-criticism are present
- helping patients notice what drains or restores their energy, using approaches such as activity scheduling or a simple “body battery” metaphor
- signposting to positive representations of neurodivergence, peersupport, or lived-experience-informed resources where appropriate

Working collaboratively with neurodevelopmental and ADHD services

Eating disorder services and neurodevelopmental services often operate separately, which can make coordinated care challenging. However, collaboration can be helpful when autism or ADHD traits significantly influence eating behaviours, treatment engagement or risk

Collaborative working may involve:

- referral for autism or ADHD assessment where clinically indicated
- joint discussion of treatment priorities, adaptations and risks
- sharing formulation and care plans between teams, with patient consent
- aligning coping strategies and adaptations across services
- coordinating medication monitoring where ADHD medication is prescribed

Where patients already have an autism or ADHD diagnosis, it can be helpful to ask about:

- how neurodivergent traits affect eating, routines, communication and treatment related tasks
- existing coping strategies, adaptations or support

- current or past ADHD medication, where relevant

Even where formal shared care arrangements are not available, clinicians can often support collaboration by communicating with primary care providers, neurodevelopmental services, ADHD specialists or autism assessment services where appropriate and with patient consent.

Integrating perspectives across services may improve understanding of how sensory processing, attention, impulsivity, emotional regulation, communication and executive functioning interact with eating disorder symptoms.

ADHD medication in eating disorder populations

Some individuals with eating disorders also receive medication for ADHD. These medications can sometimes support recovery, but they may also raise clinical questions within eating disorder treatment.

Common ADHD medications include stimulant medications such as methylphenidate and lisdexamfetamine, as well as non-stimulant medications such as atomoxetine or guanfacine.

Potential benefits

For some patients, ADHD medication may support eating disorder treatment by improving:

- attention and focus during therapy sessions
- organisation and planning for meals and daily routines
- ability to complete treatment tasks between sessions
- emotional regulation and impulsivity
- overall functioning and quality of life

For individuals with binge-type eating disorders, stimulant medication may also reduce binge eating in some cases. For

example, lisdexamfetamine is approved in several countries for the treatment of binge eating disorder.

Potential risks or considerations

ADHD medication may also present challenges that require careful monitoring.

Stimulant medications can:

- suppress appetite or reduce food intake
- make hunger cues harder to notice
- lead to weight loss in some individuals
- contribute to rebound hunger or evening binge eating when medication wears off

These effects may complicate treatment for restrictive eating disorders or individuals who are medically compromised.

Clinicians may therefore consider:

- monitoring weight and nutritional intake carefully
- discussing medication timing in relation to meals
- asking about changes in appetite, hunger cues or eating patterns
- working collaboratively with prescribing clinicians
- considering non-stimulant medication options where appropriate

Medication decisions should always be made collaboratively between the patient, prescriber and treatment team, balancing potential benefits for ADHD symptoms with the needs of eating disorder recovery.

2. Further information for clinicians

What is neurodivergence?

Neurodiversity refers to the reality that diverse brains and minds exist.

Neurodivergence describes differences in how some people process and experience the world compared with the average. Around 15–20% of the global population are estimated to be neurodivergent.

Autism and ADHD are commonly recognised forms of neurodivergence. They are neurodevelopmental differences that can affect how individuals think, communicate, regulate emotions, process sensory information and organise behaviour.

Autism and ADHD frequently co-occur. When both are present, this may be referred to as AuDHD.

Being neurodivergent does not mean something is “wrong” with a person. It reflects variation in human neurodevelopment and is understood as part of who somebody is, rather than something to be treated or “cured”.

Individuals may have different preferences for how they describe themselves. Where possible, clinicians should use the language preferred by the individual. In the absence of a stated preference, UK research suggests many autistic adults prefer identity-first language, such as “autistic person”, while recent research with adults with ADHD suggests a preference for person-first language, such as “person with ADHD”. Many neurodivergent adults also prefer terms such as “neurodivergent” over more medicalised or deficit-based language, although preferences vary across individuals and should never be assumed.

Neurodivergence often brings both strengths and challenges. Some individuals may show strong attention to detail, creativity, deep focus or analytical thinking. However, difficulties can be made worse by environments, systems or treatments designed primarily around neurotypical expectations.

An awareness of neurodivergence can help clinicians focus on understanding needs and adapting care, rather than mis-understanding differences as deficits, resistance or lack of motivation.

The biology of neurodivergence

Autism and ADHD are neurodevelopmental differences with strong genetic and biological foundations.

They are not caused by parenting style or personal failure, although life experiences can influence how someone copes, masks or presents in clinical settings.

Both show high heritability:

- autism is estimated to be 60–90% heritable
- ADHD is estimated to be around 70–80% heritable
- Family members may therefore also show related traits.

Neuroscience research suggests differences in brain networks involved in:

Autism

- sensory processing
- social cognition
- neural connectivity
- predictive processing

ADHD

- attention regulation
- impulse control
- reward processing
- emotional regulation

These differences reflect variation in brain development, rather than brain damage or illness. Understanding this can shift treatment away from blame and towards supportive, needs-based approaches.

Recognising autistic and ADHD traits

Neurodivergent traits can present differently across individuals and may change depending on stress, environment or masking.

It is also important to recognise that neurodivergent traits may present differently across gender identities and can be shaped by social expectations. For example, girls, women and gender-diverse individuals may be more likely to mask difficulties, internalise distress, or present in ways that are less consistent with traditional diagnostic stereotypes. This can contribute to delayed recognition or misdiagnosis. Clinicians should remain open to subtle or less stereotypical presentations of autism and ADHD, particularly in eating disorder settings where perfectionism, masking and internalising difficulties may already be prominent.

Common autistic traits may include:

- preference for routine, predictability and sameness
- sensory sensitivities, for example sound, smell, light, color or texture
- differences in interpreting social cues or navigating social expectations
- deep focus on particular interests or activities
- differences in noticing and experiencing internal body signals
- difficulties starting, stopping or switching tasks
- social exhaustion or masking in social situations
- overwhelm that may lead to shutdown or distress

Common ADHD traits may include:

- difficulties sustaining attention on low-interest tasks
- hyperfocus on highly engaging tasks and activities of interest
- impulsivity or acting quickly in the moment
- mental or physical restlessness
- difficulties with planning, organisation and time management
- forgetting tasks or struggling to initiate them
- strong or rapidly shifting emotions
- feeling easily overwhelmed by competing demands

How neurodivergence might impact eating disorder presentation

Autism and ADHD are both over-represented in eating disorder populations.

Estimates vary by study and measurement but research suggests:

- around 35–45% of individuals with anorexia nervosa show autistic traits or are autistic
- approximately 10–20% of people with eating disorders are autistic
- around 15–58% of people with bulimia nervosa have ADHD
- ADHD is present in 10–36% of people with binge eating disorder

Autism and ADHD can shape eating disorder presentations in different ways, including through sensory processing, interoception, predictability, attention, impulsivity, emotional regulation and attempts to manage distress.

The sections below describe some common patterns clinicians may find useful to consider. These are not fixed profiles and will vary across individuals.

How can autism influence eating disorders?

Autistic individuals often experience differences in sensory processing, need for predictability and interoception. These differences may shape eating in several ways.

For example:

- sensory sensitivities may make certain foods overwhelming
- individuals may prefer a limited range of familiar foods
- routines around meals may feel important for safety
- social eating environments may feel stressful or overstimulating
- hunger or fullness cues may be harder to recognise

Autistic individuals may also experience higher rates of social isolation, misunderstanding or bullying. These experiences can affect identity, emotional wellbeing and vulnerability to eating disorders.

Controlling food or weight may become a way to create predictability, reduce uncertainty or manage distress.

When autism is recognised and understood, treatment can often be adapted in ways that reduce distress and support eating disorder treatment engagement.

Autism beyond restrictive eating disorders

Autistic traits may influence eating across different eating disorder diagnoses. For example, sensory sensitivities, preference for routine, emotional overwhelm, and differences in recognising hunger, fullness or emotional states may all affect food choices and eating patterns.

Bingeing may sometimes function as a way to self-soothe or manage overwhelming emotions, particularly when other regulation strategies feel inaccessible.

Recognising autism across different eating disorder presentations can support more accurate formulation and more appropriate treatment adaptations.

How can ADHD influence eating disorders?

ADHD is associated with differences in attention, reward processing, impulsivity and executive functioning. These differences may influence eating patterns in several ways.

For example:

- forgetting to eat or missing meals due to hyperfocus
- difficulties and overwhelm in planning, shopping for or preparing food
- irregular eating patterns due to time blindness
- difficulty recognising hunger or fullness signals
- eating quickly or impulsively
- eating for stimulation when bored or under-stimulated
- using food to regulate emotions or reduce mental noise

ADHD may also contribute to bingeing in some individuals. Missed meals, irregular eating, emotional overwhelm, impulsivity or under-stimulation may increase vulnerability to binge eating.

Where alcohol or substance use is present, this may also interact with impulsivity, emotion regulation, eating patterns and treatment engagement.

Daily life demands such as school, work or social expectations may also feel overwhelming, increasing stress and vulnerability to eating difficulties.

Understanding ADHD can support clinicians in developing more effective and compassionate formulations.

Recognising neurodivergent needs during eating disorder treatment

Neurodivergent traits may not always be obvious during clinical assessments. Some individuals mask or camouflage their differences, particularly in structured settings such as therapy sessions.

As a result, clinicians may observe patterns during treatment that seem inconsistent or confusing. These behaviours are sometimes misinterpreted as lack of motivation, resistance or non-compliance, when they may reflect underlying neurodivergent differences and needs.

Signs that neurodivergence may be influencing treatment engagement can include:

- appearing motivated and engaged during sessions but struggling to complete homework tasks or behaviour experiments between sessions
- difficulty starting tasks such as food diaries, meal plans or cognitive exercises despite understanding their purpose at the time
- difficulty following instructions when too many steps are given at once, or when figurative or ambiguous language is used
- forgetting appointments, meal plans or homework despite wanting to engage in treatment

- becoming overwhelmed by complex worksheets or large amounts of written material
- finding it hard to identify or describe emotions during therapy
- difficulty noticing hunger, fullness or body signals used in treatment tasks
- feeling overwhelmed by meal planning, grocery shopping or food preparation
- struggling with flexible eating plans or unexpected changes to routines
- high distress around sensory aspects of food and eating, such as textures, tastes, smells, temperatures, visual aspects, sounds
- difficulty trying new foods or deviating from familiar foods, even when willing to increase overall intake
- feeling overwhelmed by group treatment settings or sensory aspects of the clinical environment
- becoming distressed when treatment expectations are unclear or unpredictable

In ADHD, clinicians may also notice:

- irregular eating patterns due to hyperfocus or time blindness
- difficulty organising meals or food shopping
- impulsive eating during periods of emotional distress or boredom
- inconsistent engagement with self-monitoring tools
- overcomplicating tasks, leading to action paralysis
- feeling overwhelmed by choice or not knowing where to start
- sensitivity to perceived criticism or rejection, which may affect the therapeutic relationship

Recognising these patterns can help clinicians shift from interpreting behaviour as resistance towards understanding potential barriers related to neurodivergence.

Further training and resources

Clinicians often report limited training in neurodiversity within eating disorder services. Accessing further learning can support more inclusive care.

Useful resources include:

- **PEACE Pathway**
— training and resources on autism, neurodivergence and eating disorders. www.peacepathway.org
- **Eating Disorders and Autism Collaborative (EDAC)**
— resources and information on autism and eating disorders. www.edacresearch.co.uk
- **PEACE adapted for CAMHS**
— www.peacepathwaybob.org
- **National Autistic Society**
— information and guidance on autism, communication, sensory needs and support. www.autism.org.uk
- **The Oliver McGowan Mandatory Training on Learning Disability and Autism**
— training designed to improve understanding and support for autistic people and people with a learning disability

Many clinicians find that improving neurodiversity awareness can enhance therapeutic relationships, improve treatment engagement and support more personalised care.

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